

A PRELIMINARY ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF ALTERNATIVE LIGNOCELLULOSIC FIBRES IN INDUSTRIAL PACKAGING

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Abstract: *this is a preliminary environmental analysis of a new packaging material that incorporates biomass of non-native invasive plants and enables the production of new high-performance packaging solutions. We compare several environmental impact categories of the bio-mass collection process used in the benchmark packaging production, with that of the proposed one. Several analysis methods indicate improvement in impact categories that relate to freshwater ecotoxicity, human carcinogenic toxicity, marine ecotoxicity, and terrestrial ecotoxicity to name a few.*

Keywords: eLCA, industrial packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

This work is part of a project that develops new packaging material for industrial purposes. The contribution to the project is the environmental life cycle analysis that accompanies different process designs developed by the partners, in order to produce the new packaging material. The environmental assessment can help favour some design decisions over others, and will be considered together with corresponding economic and social assessments.

The project is titled: learning and demonstration network for the design and production of sustainable industrial packaging made of alternative lignocellulosic fibres, hereafter referred to as LEAP. It incorporates biomass of non-native invasive plants to produce high-performance packaging solutions for heavier industrial applications. The ambition is to replace Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) packaging. More details can be found on <https://www.project-leap.com/>

At this stage we are assessing the environmental impact of a sub-process that involves the collection of biomass to produce both the benchmark and new packaging solutions. In the existing benchmark processes the Invasive Alien Plants (IAP) are harvested in a central collecting facility together with mixed biomass coming from various sources. The biomass is then either grinded and sent to composting, or dried and burned for energy production. There is no separate treatment of biomass from IAP. The proposed new collection sub-process separates the biomass coming from IAP from other biomass types already at the individual collection points. Separated biomass is transported to a central collecting facility, where each IAP species is treated individually; stalks (80% of biomass) are separated from the residues like roots and leaves, dried, and grinded into woodchips. Then, they are sent to cellulose pulp production process while the residues (20 % of biomass) for composting. By this change in collection process the IAP biomass can be used as a raw material for cellulose pulp production, a product with higher added value compared to compost and energy produced. See Figure.

Figure 1. A schematic of the biomass collection process for the benchmark and new concepts.

2 METHODS AND RESULTS

The contribution of this work to the LEAP project is the environmental assessment of the two biomass collection processes. SINTEF used the software SimaPro to simulate models for both processes, while the project partner, ICP, did the process modelling and data collection as far as environmental impacts are concerned. Several analysis methods were tested to see if there is a general conclusion about which impact categories are improved or degraded. We selected the following methods: ReCipe, IMPACT endPt, and IMPACT midPt. Selection was based on the number of processes each method can account for when simulating the biomass collections. Other methods can be used as well.

The results at this point should be interpreted in relative terms, rather than absolute ones because of the high-level abstraction in the models and crude data available at this time. That said, the following relative changes were observed. Negative numbers indicate an improvement.

Table 1. Relative changes using the ReCipe method.

Impact category - ReCipe	Unit	Relative change
<i>Fine particulate matter formation</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-10.07
<i>Fossil resource scarcity</i>	<i>USD2013</i>	-3.13
<i>Freshwater ecotoxicity</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-12.47
<i>Freshwater eutrophication</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-8.43
<i>Global warming, Freshwater ecosystems</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-1.72
<i>Global warming, Human health</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-1.72
<i>Global warming, Terrestrial ecosystems</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-1.72
<i>Human carcinogenic toxicity</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-14.14
<i>Human non-carcinogenic toxicity</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-3.36
<i>Ionizing radiation</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-0.49
<i>Land use</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-50.92
<i>Marine ecotoxicity</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-12.22
<i>Marine eutrophication</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-1.41
<i>Mineral resource scarcity</i>	<i>USD2013</i>	-45.69
<i>Ozone formation, Human health</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-7.59
<i>Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-7.59
<i>Stratospheric ozone depletion</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-5.33
<i>Terrestrial acidification</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-5.01
<i>Terrestrial ecotoxicity</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-83.46
<i>Water consumption, Aquatic ecosystems</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-3.53
<i>Water consumption, Human health</i>	<i>DALY</i>	-1.03
<i>Water consumption, Terrestrial ecosystem</i>	<i>species.yr</i>	-1.36

Table 2. Relative changes using the IMPACT endPt. method.

Impact category – IMPACT endPt.	Unit	Relative change
Climate change, ecosystem quality, long	PDF.m2.yr	-1.07
Climate change, ecosystem quality, short	PDF.m2.yr	-0.88
Climate change, human health, long term	DALY	-1.07
Climate change, human health, short term	DALY	-0.88
Freshwater acidification	PDF.m2.yr	-5.97
Freshwater ecotoxicity, long term	PDF.m2.yr	-15.57
Freshwater ecotoxicity, short term	PDF.m2.yr	-14.41
Freshwater eutrophication	PDF.m2.yr	-25.21
Human toxicity cancer, long term	DALY	-9.32
Human toxicity cancer, short term	DALY	-16.00
Human toxicity non-cancer, long term	DALY	-1.43
Human toxicity non-cancer, short term	DALY	0.46
Ionizing radiation, ecosystem quality	PDF.m2.yr	-7.35
Ionizing radiation, human health	DALY	-3.12
Land occupation, biodiversity	PDF.m2.yr	-9.93
Land transformation, biodiversity	PDF.m2.yr	204.81
Marine acidification, long term	PDF.m2.yr	-1.10
Marine acidification, short term	PDF.m2.yr	-1.10
Marine eutrophication	PDF.m2.yr	-9.76
Ozone layer depletion	DALY	-48.91
Particulate matter formation	DALY	-7.64
Photochemical oxidant formation	DALY	-6.74
Terrestrial acidification	PDF.m2.yr	-5.94
Thermally polluted water	PDF.m2.yr	-1.28
Water availability, freshwater ecosys.	PDF.m2.yr	-0.51
Water availability, human health	DALY	0.20
Water availability, terrestrial ecosys.	PDF.m2.yr	-2.09

Table 3. Relative changes using the IMPACT midPt. method.

Impact category – IMPACT midPt.	Unit	Relative change
Climate change, long term	kg CO2 eq	-1.81
Climate change, short term	kg CO2 eq	-1.71
Fossil and nuclear energy use	MJ deprived	-2.83
Freshwater acidification	kg SO2 eq	-7.39
Freshwater ecotoxicity	CTUe	-18.60
Freshwater eutrophication	kg PO4 eq	-28.85
Human toxicity cancer	CTUh	-14.34
Human toxicity non-cancer	CTUh	-0.36
Ionizing radiation	Bq C-14 eq	-4.00
Land occupation, biodiversity	m2yr arable	-12.54
Land transformation, biodiversity	m2yr arable	469.18
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	-11.21
Mineral resources use	kg deprived	-44.08
Ozone layer depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	-163.73
Particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	-9.44

<i>Photochemical oxidant formation</i>	<i>kg NMVOC eq</i>	<i>-7.75</i>
<i>Terrestrial acidification</i>	<i>kg SO2 eq</i>	<i>-7.22</i>
<i>Water scarcity</i>	<i>m3 world eq</i>	<i>-1.56</i>

These results only indicate that the new collection process is promising from an environmental perspective, nothing else. Absolute improvement, or degradation, numbers have little meaning at this stage. The reader should not interpret the results as: the new process causes an improvement, or degradation, in category x or y, as there is no causal relationship established at this stage. Yet, the reader can benefit from the modelling process in SimaPro, or the like, in terms of processes selected, and the logic connecting them if he is to replicate a similar biomass collection process.

3 CONCLUSION

This work presented a SimaPro “model” of two biomass collection processes with the LEAP project. Comparing the two models showed a number of environmental improvements across several impact categories. This further encouraged the project team to continue developing the new packaging material. Continuous environmental assessments are necessary as we extend on the biomass collection process and integrate it with the overall production.

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